

1 **Induction of a Hox locus non-coding RNA, HOTAIR, in human malignancy.**

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6 HOX factors mediate and sustain transformation. We studied total transcription by RNA-sequencing in the
7 primary tumors of humans with osteosarcoma. We describe here activation of HOTAIR, a long non-coding
8 RNA encoded by the HOXC locus adjacent to HOXC11, in human cancer. The data support a role for
9 HOTAIR as a mediator of oncogenesis and metastasis.

10 Citations

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